

Roman2023	Tuesday, June 20	Wednesday, June 21	Thursday, June 22	Friday, June 23
9:30 to 10:00 AM		Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break
10:00 AM to 12:00 PM		Session 3: Invited talk and contributed talks	Session 5: Invited talk and contributed talks	Session 7: Invited talk and contributed talks
12:00 to 1:00 PM	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch
1:00 to 3:00 PM	Session 1: Welcome, Mission and Science overviews	Session 4: Invited talk and contributed talks	Session 6: Invited talk and contributed talks	Session 8: Invited talk and contributed talks
3:00 to 3:30 PM	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break
3:30 to 4:00 PM	Session 2: Invited talk and contributed talks	Science Writers Workshop	Poster session II	Conference summary
4:00 to 4:30 PM				
4:30 to 5:00 PM		STScI Public Lecture		
5:00 to 5:30 PM				
5:30 to 6:00 PM		Poster session I	Conference Reception Appetizers provided and cash bar available	
6:00 to 6:30 PM		Small Group Dinners at various local restaurants		
6:30 to 7:00 PM				
7:00 to 7:30 PM	Astronomy on Tap			
<i>All times EDT</i>				